

Performance Analysis of Single Band and Multi-Band Transponders for CD-ROADM based S-, C-, L-band WDM networks

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Abstract: This paper compares single-band and multi-band transponders for CD-ROADM nodes in UWB-WDM Networks, covering the S, C, and L bands. We also consider various add/drop configurations with WSS of different sizes.

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1. Introduction

The increasing demand for internet bandwidth, fueled by the rise of cloud services, video streaming, and artificial intelligence applications, has created a need for greater capacity. With a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 25% and based on moderate traffic forecasts, spectrum demand is projected to reach 50 THz by 2031 [1]. As this demand grows, the need for high-capacity optical fiber links will become increasingly critical. One of the options is to use UWB-WDM systems with a wide range of wavelengths, typically 1260 nm to 1625 nm, covering the O, E, S, C, and L-band. A key component of a ROADM node is the Wavelength Selective Switches (WSS). Various ROADM node architectures have been described in the literature [2, 3], with two notable types being Colorless and Directionless (CD) and Colorless, Directionless, and Contentionless (CDC). A CD-ROADM can add or drop any wavelength at any port (colorless) and route the signal to any output (directionless). Figure 1a shows the CD-based ROADM node 'D' architecture part of the example network. It includes one incoming and one outgoing WSS per direction. In a typical ROADM with degree- N , $N-1$ ports are used for express traffic, connecting to other directions, while the remaining WSS ports are utilized for the add/drop stage. In this setup, the add/drop stage consists of add/drop blocks composed of two pairs of WSSs connected back-to-back via a link, referred to as a contention link. WSS offers a range of configurations to suit different network demands. Commercially, standard configurations include 1x16 and 1x32 switches, which define the number of available ports. However, technological advancements suggest that 1x64 WSS will soon be available, and future developments could support up to 1x128 ports. Additionally, in add/drop stages, each block comprises a set number of ports, allowing it to support a limited number of transponders. If more transponders are needed, additional add/drop blocks must be introduced. However, increasing the number of blocks also necessitates more ports per direction in the WSS, which impacts overall system complexity and cost.

In this paper, we consider two types of transponders: **Single Band Transponder (SBT)**: These are dedicated to specific bands. From the set of transponders T , which is further divided into subsets T_s , T_c , and T_l corresponds to the S-band, C-band, and L-band, respectively. When a connection requests a transponder for a specific band (e.g., the C-band), an available transponder from the corresponding subset (e.g., T_c) is assigned. The distribution of transponders across T_s , T_c , and T_l must be considered carefully, as illustrated in the results later. In this paper, we examine both uniform and non-uniform distribution of transponders across the S, C, and L bands. **Multi-Band Transponder (MBT)**: These transponders provide more flexibility by assigning any transponder from the set T , regardless of the specific band. In this paper, we present a performance analysis of SBT and MBT for CD ROADM nodes in WDM systems across the S, C, and L bands, considering WSS of different sizes with varying add/drop blocks.

2. Routing, Band, Spectrum and Transponder Assignment (RBSTA) Algorithm

In Figure 1b, we consider an undirected network graph G that consists of a V set of nodes $v \in V$, E set of Edges $e \in E$ and each fiber link e is between pair of nodes (i,j) where $(i,j) \in E$, $i \in V$, $j \in V$. Each fiber has multiple bands (S, C, and L). A Lightpath Request $LR(s,d,SS')$ is defined by the tuple: source node s , destination node d and required spectrum slots SS' . Each node has one or several add/drop blocks and a limited number of transponders T . The flowchart in Figure 1b outlines the process for reserving resources (continuous spectrum slot and transponder)

Fig. 1: (a) CD-ROADM node architecture of node ‘D’ (part of an example network G with 5 nodes (vertices), 7 links (edges), and 8 spectrum slots) with SBT and MBT, (b) The flowchart shows the reservation of resources from source node s to destination node d .

for a connection. This problem is called RBSTA. When an LR arrives, the algorithm searches for a path with available spectrum slots from s to d . The search prioritizes spectrum bands sequentially: first in the C-band, then in the L-band, and finally in the S-band. Once a path with available slots is found within a band, the next step is to check at the end nodes the availability of slots on the contention link of the add/drop block and also the availability of transponders. If both slots and transponders are available, the “first fit” method is used to select the slot, and the algorithm allocates them to establish the lightpath from s to d . If no slots are available during pathfinding, or if there are no slots on the contention link or transponders on the add/drop block, go for another band if available; otherwise, if no bands are available, the request is blocked.

3. Results and Discussions

We conduct simulations on a Spanish Telefonica optical backbone network with 65 nodes and 135 bi-directional links, having an average nodal degree of 3.5. Each link has S (7 THz), C (6 THz) and L (6 THz) bands. Considering that each connection requires a single 200 GHz slot (with a 12.5 GHz granularity), the number of slots on each band are S (35), C (30), and L (30). The 65 nodes are split into 11 core nodes and 54 service nodes. A non-uniform traffic model is used: 66% of traffic occurs between core and service nodes, while 34% is between core-core nodes. Service nodes communicate with their nearest core node(s). Connection requests are generated dynamically using a Poisson distribution, with a mean Holding Time of one unit and a variable mean Inter-Arrival Time, resulting in traffic loads ranging from 650 to 1300 Er. Simulations include 10 iterations, each processing 100,000 requests, with blocking probability results shown at a 95% confidence interval. This work evaluates two WSS configurations at the add/drop stage, specifically 1x64 and 1x128 WSSs. Figure 2 illustrates the connection blocking probability and the average and maximum number of active client ports per node under different traffic loads for various WSS sizes, each with a corresponding number of add/drop blocks and we assume in all cases a fixed amount of transponders at each node, regardless on how these are distributed into add/drop blocks. In Figure 2, Tps is for Transponders, A/D for add-drop blocks, S+C+L for MBT, S, C, L for SBT, CN for core nodes and SN for

Fig. 2: Performance parameters measured for various offered traffic for Telefonica topology assuming 256 Tps. service nodes. This work uses a CDC-based WDM system as the baseline for comparison. With a 1x128 WSS and two A/D blocks, the impact of contention (low number of A/D) is higher. Compared to the CDC baseline and at around 1% blocking, the performance of 1x128 MBT is approx 23.08% worse, and SBT is approx 30.77% worse. As the number of A/D blocks increases, such as for 1x64 WSS with four A/D blocks, more connections can be accommodated. Therefore, the performance of a CD-based 1x64 WSS (MBT and SBT {96, 80, 80} Tps) matches that of a CDC, indicating that beyond a certain number of A/D blocks, the CD 1x64 behaves similarly to CDC. Also, as shown in Figure 2 b and c, where the average and maximum active client ports per node are nearly the same at the core and service nodes for CDC and 1x64. When evaluating the performance of SBT and MBT, it becomes clear that with a lower number of A/D blocks (e.g., 1x128 WSS), SBT performs worse. This is because each band in SBT is allocated a dedicated set of Tps, reducing the chances of finding an available band slot and corresponding Tp at a given traffic load, leading to blocking due to insufficient Tps and a low number of A/D blocks. In contrast, MBT has greater flexibility in Tp assignment, meaning most blocking occurs at the A/D stage due to contention. As a result, some Tps remain unused in MBT due to contention at certain links. With the same number of Tps, increasing the number of A/D blocks shifts the primary cause of blocking to the lack of available Tps and spectrum slots, similar to the behaviour of a CDC ROADM. Intuitively, when further increasing the number of A/D blocks to 8 for a 1x32 WSS or 16 for a 1x16 WSS, performance would remain comparable to CDC, although this would require more ports per direction in the WSS, which significantly raises costs. A critical factor in SBT is the distribution of Tps across the different bands. If the Tps are distributed uniformly (like {96, 80, 80} Tps), the performance of SBT with higher contention links is comparable to both CDC and MBT. However, if the distribution is non-uniform, such as allocating more Tps to the C and/or L bands than the S-band (which has more slots), blocking occurs due to insufficient Tps. Another important aspect is the allocation of add/drop (A/D) blocks to core and service nodes. Due to non-uniform traffic, assigning the same number of A/D blocks to both leads to resource wastage and higher costs, though in the simulation, we assume equal A/D blocks at all nodes. One can take reference from Figure 2b and c, which suggests that one A/D block is sufficient for service nodes, while a higher number can be used at core nodes.

4. Conclusions

This paper presents the performance comparison for SBT and MBT used in CD-ROADM-based UWB-WDM networks. In summary, with a sufficient number of add/drop blocks and an appropriate distribution of transponders across the bands, CD-ROADM with SBT can provide the optimal balance between cost and performance.

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